

The Poetics of Memory in Contemporary Spanish Poetry: Antonio Machado, Luis Cernuda and Jaime Gil de Biedma

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ABSTRACT

Literature is one of the richest fields for exploring cultural representations of memory. This article examines the works of three major twentieth-century Spanish poets—Antonio Machado, Luis Cernuda, and Jaime Gil de Biedma—demonstrating how their poetry articulates a distinctive poetics of memory. Through a selection of poems, it becomes evident that this tradition, which has profoundly shaped contemporary Spanish literature, adapts to different historical and social contexts. Memory in these works is not merely a theme but a structuring force that shapes the poet's self-narrative, intertwining personal and collective pasts. Autobiographical reflection in their poetry often engages with themes of loss, exile, desire, and personal identity, reinforcing the idea that memory is both an act of retrieval and a means of self-construction. This poetics of memory developed in dialogue with the emerging field of memory studies, drawing particularly on the philosophy of Henri Bergson, whose ideas on time and recollection deeply influenced Machado. His vision of memory as fluid and subjective became a foundation upon which later poets, including Cernuda and Gil de Biedma, built their own explorations of the self and the past.

KEYWORDS

Spanish poetry; memory in literature; Antonio Machado; Luis Cernuda; Jaime Gil de Biedma

Introduction

Memory has always been an important literary theme, from the distant past to the present day. The Spanish literary tradition is no exception, and in its canon we can find numerous authors who, like Jorge Manrique or Gustavo Adolfo Bécquer, have used some aspects of memory to articulate their poetic ideas. At the beginning of the twentieth century, there appeared a group of poets who made the theme a fundamental element of their respective work, giving it a dimension and a scope that it had not had until then. When introduced into literature, memory often becomes one of the primary forces shaping the narrative of the writer's life, thus constituting a fundamental aspect of autobiographical writing.¹ In this article, I will focus on three of the most important Spanish poets of the twentieth century: Antonio Machado, Luis Cernuda, and Jaime Gil de Biedma. I will try to demonstrate that their ideas about the nature of poetic creation, although divergent in many respects, converge on one fundamental point, which is the consideration of memory as a privileged poetic material. This will allow me to situate them within what I will call the 'poetics of memory', a clearly identifiable movement in contemporary Spanish literature, whose main referents are the three aforementioned authors.

The development of the poetics of the three selected authors practically coincides with the evolution of the field known as memory studies. This approach was first developed by the sociologist Maurice Halbwachs, a student of Henri Bergson, in his 1925 work *Les cadres sociaux de la mémoire* (*The Social Frameworks of Memory*). Theoretical interest in memory appeared in the 1980s: authors such as Pierre Nora or Aleida and Jan Assmann founded the field of memory studies as we know it today (Erl 2008). From the beginning, this emerging field was strongly focused on sociological, historical, or political issues, and partly ignored other cultural or artistic issues, such as literary studies and aesthetics. In recent years, there has been a growing interest in broadening the scope of memory studies in this direction.² In this sense, a number of approaches to the 'poetics of memory' have been published by various authors, albeit from very heterogeneous theoretical perspectives (Brewster 2005; Gaxha 2022; Rapport and Hartill 2010). More specifically, Astrid Erl has identified five theoretical models for applying memory studies to the literary field:

First, ‘literature as *ars memoriae*’ captures research on memory which explores literature’s role in cultural mnemonics. The focus of interest has been on the art of memory of the Middle Ages and early modern period. Second, a ‘memory of literature’ is highlighted in studies that look at the return of elements from earlier works of art. This return is often conceived of in terms of intertextuality and intermediality. An important forerunner of this research direction is the art historian Aby Warburg. Third, ‘memory of literature’ can also denote processes of canon formation and literary historiography. Fourth, the concept of ‘memory in literature’ captures work done on the forms of the aesthetic representation or: staging, of memory. Fifth, ‘literature as a medium of cultural memory’ is used here to designate a direction of research which is interested in literature as an active force in memory culture. (Erl 2011, 67–68)

In this article, I will examine the fourth of the models mentioned by Erl, the concept of ‘memory in literature’ (or, more specifically, ‘memory in poetry’), and I will focus my attention on the ways in which the three selected poets make aesthetic use of themes related to memory. In this way, I will be able to identify the notion of a ‘poetics of memory’, which is adapted to the time and intention of each author.

Although they are not strictly contemporaneous in the chronological sense of the term, the three selected poets are representative of successive links that together constitute the chain of contemporary Spanish poetry. Here, the notion of contemporaneity will be employed in the broader sense it generally assumes in literary historiography, primarily associated with the modernist and postmodernist aesthetic movements of the twentieth century. Furthermore, this historiographical notion can relate to the more sociologically oriented idea of a literary generation (Mironescu 2022). Machado, Cernuda, and Gil de Biedma belong to three successive generations, and thus, although their lifespans do not coincide within the same temporal frame, they nonetheless tend to overlap. This continuity—further substantiated by recognisable relations of influence traceable in their texts—allows all three to be grouped under the shared label of contemporary poets.

Poetry as autobiography

Before engaging in the detailed study of the poetry of these three authors, it is necessary to establish a theoretical framework that allows us to understand why this poetics of memory is read as autobiographical writing. From a historical perspective, poetry and the autobiographical representation of the poet have always been intertwined. In Classical Antiquity, for example, phenomena such as the *sphragis* can be found—brief passages inserted in longer poems (such as Virgil’s *Georgics*) that function as miniaturised autobiographies, insofar as they provide an identity seal of the poet. But there are also entire poetic genres, particularly love poetry from its very origins (Propertius, Ovid, etc.), where the autobiographical presence of the poet, whether genuine or entirely fictional, proves essential.³ The same can be said of medieval Christian poetry, with particularly relevant examples such as Dante Alighieri’s *Divine Comedy*, sometimes viewed as a case of autobiographical writing (Watt 2021).

However, as various scholars have pointed out, contemporary theorisation of the autobiographical genre has almost always privileged prose genres over poetic ones. For example, the famous characterisation offered by Philippe Lejeune (1975, 14) defines autobiography as a prose genre, thereby excluding poetry.⁴ As Gill and Waters (2009, 3–4) note, it is most likely that such critical assumptions are due to the predominance of the lyrical mode in modern poetry, which has often led to poetry being understood as a literary expression inseparably linked to the Self, that is, to the real Self of the poet (Hamburger 1993). Thus, poetry could not be autobiographical simply because its enunciative mode would render recourse to the poet’s life unnecessary (as it would be redundant). In this way, autobiography would be definitively assimilated to narrative genres in which the fictional Self does not have to be identified with the authorial Self.

Since this understanding of autobiography is manifestly narrow and unsatisfactory, it becomes necessary to broaden the theoretical approach to accommodate more diverse poetic works, along the lines of what some scholars have recently undertaken (Görbert, Hansen, and Wolf 2021; Takolander 2017). Indeed, if we start from the premise that poetry does not necessarily have to present a lyrical expressive mode but has always been associated with fictional voices that substitute the authorial self, the possibility of an autobiographical poetry becomes evident. Furthermore, contemporary poetry itself provides a factual basis for asserting that autobiographical genres can manifest themselves in verse and not only in prose. The frequent dissociations of identity in Surrealist or avant-garde poetry in general, or the confessional poetry of authors

such as Ted Hughes or Sylvia Plath, are just a few examples of this. In the case at hand, contemporary Spanish literature, I will attempt to demonstrate that various forms of autobiographical writing have played a significant role, as has already been partially noted in some studies (Lerro 2017).

Specifically, I intend to show how the autobiographical writing of contemporary Spanish poets is mediated through memory, understood not only as a theme but also as a poetic motivation. Memory is by no means alien to autobiographical writing, as some theorists have recognised in recent years. Particularly insightful in this regard is Olney's contribution (2014), which highlights the importance of memory in the very ontology of autobiography. After all, the past, from which the vital materials for autobiographical writing are drawn, does not truly exist except through recollection. In this way, memory plays a decisive mediating role in all autobiographical recreation.

It is precisely at this point that we perceive the complex dialectic between literature and life, which can never be entirely conceived as separate. If autobiographical writing demonstrates anything, it is that the *bios* never appears in a direct and pure form, but is always subjected to some kind of literary elaboration. Often, this elaboration is narrative, but in other cases, it is poetic. The contemporary Spanish authors I will examine in the following sections, approached from this theoretical ground, constitute paradigmatic examples of the intricate relationship between memory and literaturised *bios*. For these authors, the recollection of past biographical experience constitutes the starting point for its literary work. By recovering traces of their past life, poets such as Machado, Cernuda, or Gil de Biedma manage to endow their respective writings with a tone that transcends the conventional boundaries of narrative genres. Through poetic stylisation, the autobiographical material becomes part of a common repertoire of literary myths and topoi that help the poet understand their own life journey. In this way, the poetics of memory emerges as a privileged framework for shaping an authorial consciousness that intricately interweaves life and literature, establishing a profound and enduring connection between the two.

Antonio Machado: word in time

Antonio Machado (1875–1939) is widely regarded as one of the founders of contemporary Spanish poetry (De Ros 2015). His literary beginnings were marked by the strong influence of Rubén Darío's Modernism around 1900. The influence of Modernism can be seen in his first book, *Soledades* (*Solitudes*, 1903), although Machado evolved rapidly, eliminating Modernist excesses, and developing a much more introspective style, which emerged in his second, expanded edition, *Soledades. Galerías. Otros poemas* (*Solitudes. Galleries. Other Poems*, 1907). This last book contains some of his texts most directly related to memory, especially to the nostalgic evocation of his childhood in Seville. This is demonstrated in the poem 'El limo-nero lánguido suspende ...' ('The languid lemon tree suspends ...'), in which Machado uses various symbols to evoke his childhood experiences, now recalled on a spring afternoon:

Sí, te recuerdo, tarde alegre y clara,
casi de primavera,
tarde sin flores, cuando me traías el
buen perfume de la hierbabuena, y de
la buena albahaca,
que tenía mi madre en sus macetas.⁵ (Machado 1979, 80)⁶

Sensual recreation, linked to the persistence in memory of a specific space (the courtyard of Seville) and mediated by the comforting presence of the mother figure, is one of the central themes of Machado's work at this stage. Time is generally accepted as the central concern of Machado's poetics (Hutman 1969, 49), and in his next book, *Campos de Castilla* (*Fields of Castile*, 1912), landscape takes on an increasingly important role. In this case, memory has collective rather than individual connotations. Nostalgia appears not so much for a lost childhood as for the past of his homeland, following the ideological line of the generation of 1989 (Unamuno, Baroja, Azorín). In the poem 'A orillas del Duero' ('On the banks of the Duero'), the poet's contemplation of the landscape leads him to lament the miserable Castile that once gave us epic heroes such as Rodrigo Díaz de Vivar and is now in decline. In a Heraclitean tone, Machado wonders if Spain's former splendour is gone forever: '¿Pasó? Sobre sus campos aún el fantasma yerra / de un pueblo que ponía a Dios sobre la guerra'⁷⁴ (1979, 138). The figure of the mother, which

was positively associated with his childhood in the previous poems, is transformed in these disenchanting verses into a 'stepmother' ('madrstra') who only produces 'louts' ('ganapanes').

In 1911, Antonio Machado moved to Paris, where he attended the classes of Henri Bergson. The influence of the French philosopher was crucial to his poetic development.⁸ In his book *Matter and Memory* (1896), Bergson distinguished between two main types of memory: an automatic one based on repetition for utilitarian purposes, and a free or spiritual memory, based on involuntary evocation. This second type of memory, which for Bergson is the true one, represents a qualitative change with respect to the purely automatic type of memory, because it implies duration (*durée*), that is, the prolongation of the past in the present. In this way, human perception is always mediated by a series of buried memories that are progressively superimposed and that flow spontaneously, sometimes surprisingly, through intuitions. It goes without saying that this philosophical theory fits very well with the literary conception of many writers of the time, including Marcel Proust and James Joyce (Ladrón and Soledad 2004, 4). Bergson's concept, which already had a strong literary base, lends itself easily to poetic application: the intuition from which involuntary memory flows will be none other than artistic intuition, the true trigger of the writer's self-reflection. It is from the philosophical perspective adopted from Bergson that Machado returns to the question of personal memory in relation to childhood.

The collection of poems *Campos de Castilla* opens with one of Machado's most famous compositions, 'Retrato' ('Portrait'). It is interesting to note that the first quatrain of this poem traces a characteristic path, the central axis of which is memory. 'Mi infancia son recuerdos de un patio de Sevilla, / y un huerto claro donde madura el limonero; / mi juventud, veinte años en tierras de Castilla; / mi historia, algunos casos que recordar no quiero'⁹ (Machado 1979, 136). First, Machado defines his childhood as 'memories of a courtyard in Seville', appealing to a Bergsonian way of evoking the past in the present. However, the quatrain ends in a contrary position, stating that his personal history contains 'some events I don't want to remember'. These four lines represent a paradoxical shift from involuntary recollection to voluntary forgetting, from a childhood that he delights in to a youth that he critically rejects. Although there has been some debate about the identification of the 'events' that the poet says he does not want to remember, it seems that the most accurate interpretation of the verse is the one that refers to the love affairs that marked Machado's youth. This aspect of his life seems to have posed a moral problem for the author at the time of writing 'Retrato' (Urrutia 1976, 925). In any case, the most important feature that I want to highlight here is that this self-portrait of the poet begins with the theme of memory, both in its pleasant evocation of childhood and in its unpleasant recollection of situations that he now rejects. Thus, memory, like its counterpart, forgetting, constitutes the poet's identity.

Machado was forced to return from Paris when his wife, the young Leonor Izquierdo, fell ill with tuberculosis. Leonor lived to see the publication of the first edition of *Campos de Castilla*, a book that would bring Machado great literary success. But the death of his wife in 1912 was a turning point in his life and poetry. From then on, the theme of memory would be transformed again and would reach new heights in what is commonly called the 'ciclo de Leonor', a collection of poems written between 1912 and 1913 that contains some of Machado's best writing. This poetic cycle was included in the second edition of *Campos de Castilla*, which, in turn, was included in the volume of *Poesías completas* (*Complete poetry*) published in 1917. In this 'Leonor cycle' we find the poem 'Recuerdos' ('Memories'), an almost exclusively descriptive composition in which the poet, travelling by train through the Andalusian countryside, evokes images of the landscape of Soria that he is leaving behind and which is inevitably linked to his wife, who is never mentioned. However, images of the landscape are not evoked directly, but through memory: the river Guadalquivir is used to remind the reader of the river Duero, and the Andalusian olive trees, the Castilian holm oaks.¹⁰ Machado now returns to the land of his childhood, which he missed in his early poems, but now with the added nostalgia of the loss of his wife in Castilian lands. The theme of the poem is undoubtedly the loss of his wife, but Machado emphasises her absence by excluding her from the text and avoiding any explicit mention of her death. What remains is the sensory suggestion of a pleasant landscape that recedes, a space that the reader must identify with the loss of Leonor.

Very similar features can be found in another of Machado's best compositions, his poetic letter to José María Palacio, written in 1913. The poem is addressed to a friend of the poet, who is asked a series of questions about the arrival of spring in Soria. Once again, there are allusions to the river Duero and the Moncayo mountain, elements of the Castilian landscape that appear repeatedly in *Campos de Castilla*. Once again, the

poet pauses to focus his senses on the colours and smells of the environment he remembers from afar. And once again, there is no explicit mention of Leonor, except for a fleeting allusion in the last lines: ‘Con los primeros lirios / y las primeras rosas de las huertas, / en una tarde azul, sube al Espino, / al alto espino donde está su tierra ...’¹¹ (Machado 1979, 199). The Espino is a hill near Soria where Leonor was buried (Gullón 1986, 137). The purpose of the poem is therefore to ask José María Palacio to bring flowers to Leonor’s grave. Machado articulates a long descriptive paraphrase of Leonor’s land (Soria), so that, in his memory, the sensual evocation of the landscape coincides with the evocation of his deceased wife. It is a kind of impersonal elegy in which the poet’s feelings are not represented, but only suggested by the sensations recovered by the memory of the environment.

As we can see with the death of Leonor and the cycle of poems dedicated to her, Machado’s poetics of memory took on a more elegiac but also more subtle tone, blending the personal nostalgia of his first book with the description of the landscape that dominates *Campos de Castilla*. The process has been rightly appreciated by Geoffrey Ribbans:

The natural objects selected are the familiar ones of Machado’s earlier descriptive poems, and they are evoked with the same evident affection and precise detail; exclamations are employed to reinforce the emotional impact of such features from Nature as the late Spring and the coloration of the Moncayo. As always, colour is an important factor, and is supported by sound and hints of taste, smell and touch. There is however an essential difference from the earlier experiences; once personally savoured, these objects are now only remembered and surmised, in a distinctive blend of memory and conjecture. (Ribbans 1997, 85)

This is an excellent formulation of the tone that Machado’s more mature poetry achieves: ‘a distinctive blend of memory and conjecture’. This is achieved because Machado, managing to overcome the emotional crisis triggered by the death of his wife, focuses on the theme of memory in relation to the separate themes of dreams and imagination. In a poem from *Soledades. Galerías. Otros poemas*, Machado wrote: ‘De toda la memoria, sólo vale / el don preclaro de evocar los sueños’.¹² (1979, 131). Aguirre (1973, 232–233) contends that these verses exemplify Machado’s characteristic synthesis of Symbolist motifs, in which intuition is intertwined with reflexivity, and he establishes a comparison with a composition by Cernuda. In this way, the concept of memory is significantly expanded: it is no longer about remembering childhood experiences, landscapes, or loved ones, but about remembering things dreamed or imagined.¹³ This leads Machado to a new chapter in the development of his poetics of memory, which is particularly evident in his last book, *Juan de Mairena* (1936). It is a miscellaneous work proposed as a compilation of the writings of a fictitious author, Juan de Mairena, who often comments on his own verses and those of his teacher, the also fictitious Abel Martín. Like Fernando Pessoa, Antonio Machado thus creates two heteronyms that serve to distance himself from his own poetic discourse, while at the same time commenting on it reflectively. Some scholars have interpreted *Juan de Mairena* as a second stage in the career of Antonio Machado: the poetic stage would have been ended around 1915 and would have been followed by a more philosophical stage (Sánchez Barbudo 1954, 110).¹⁴

But if we look at Antonio Machado’s career from the point of view of the development of his poetics of memory, we can understand much better the unity of his literary project. The creation of different poetic heteronyms must be understood in relation to the poet’s Bergsonian idea of memory. For Machado, memory is the true shaper of personal identity: the subject depends on the set of memories of the past that have led him to his present. It is therefore enough to change one’s memories (by dreaming or imagining alternative ones) in order to change one’s identity. In this way, Machado’s poetic work is transformed when it is created behind one of his fictional masks, Juan de Mairena or Abel Martín. Each has their own way of writing poetry and their own metaphysical system because each has an individual personal history, a way of appropriating time through the word. This confirms the formula with which Machado summed up the definition of what poetry meant to him: ‘palabra en el tiempo’ (1979, 298), ‘word in time’.

Luis Cernuda: where Oblivion Dwells

Luis Cernuda’s literary career was initially linked to the so-called Generation of 1927, a group of young poets who incorporated the language of the avant-garde (mainly surrealism) into the traditional forms of Spanish poetry. His life (1902–1963), on the other hand, was traumatically affected by the experience of

exile, which he faced from 1938 onwards. As a result, his poetic work is divided into two major periods, separated by the Spanish Civil War. Cernuda's fate was also shaped by these circumstances: although he received only limited recognition in Spain during his lifetime, and the prevailing indifference or hostility of his countrymen became a central theme of his later poetry, his reception began to show signs of improvement towards the end of his life. It was only with the new writers of the 1960s, such as Jaime Gil de Biedma, that his undeniable poetic ability was properly recognised.

Cernuda's early poems, written between 1924 and 1927, belong to the 'impressionistic symbolism' (Harris 1973, 5) movement cultivated at that time by Juan Ramón Jiménez, the other leading figure in Spanish poetry at the beginning of the century, along with Antonio Machado. Although this was the predominant poetic tone among his contemporaries (Salinas, Alberti, Guillén), Cernuda's first collection of poems was not well received, and the author quickly moved in other aesthetic directions. Like his contemporaries, he was strongly influenced by surrealism at the end of the 1920s, which was evident in his 1929 book *Un río, un amor (A River, A Love)*. This continued in 1931 with the publication of *Los placeres prohibidos (Forbidden Pleasures)*, a book in which the surrealist technique allowed him to give free rein to the public defence of homoerotic love, following the example of André Gide. But Cernuda also quickly outgrew the surrealist vogue and developed a much more personal voice in his fifth book, *Donde habite el olvido (Where Oblivion Dwells, 1934)*, a collection of poems often described as neo-romantic, and heavily influenced by Spanish Romantic poet Gustavo Adolfo Bécquer.

Memory is not a major theme in Cernuda's early poems, but in *Donde habite el olvido* it takes on a new importance.¹⁵ As the title of the book itself suggests, the main interest of the poet at this point is not memory, but its negative counterpart, oblivion. Indeed, Zubiaur (2002, 179–230), the scholar who has most extensively addressed this subject, argues that oblivion, together with reality and desire (the two notions that give their title to Cernuda's collected works and which probably stem from his reading of Schopenhauer), constitutes the fundamental trinity of his poetics.¹⁶ *Donde habite el olvido* is a collection essentially inspired by great disappointment in love, which Cernuda probably suffered around 1932 with the Galician actor Serafín Ferro. The theme of memory is mixed with that of desire, whose conflict with reality becomes the central concern of the poet, described in one verse as a 'errabundo mendigo, recordando, deseando'¹⁷ (Cernuda 1993, 209).¹⁸ In this way, the painful memory of his frustrated love is linked to the disillusioned memory of his idealised youth. The failure in love is also a failure in life, which comes to disenchant the amorous desire of the poet's youth:

No es el amor quien muere,
Somos nosotros mismos.
Inocencia primera Abolida
en deseo,
Olvido de sí mismo en otro olvido,
Rimas entrelazadas,
¿Por qué vivir si desaparecéis un día?¹⁹ (Cernuda 1993, 210)

The solution to this desperate situation is to end it drastically, either through death or oblivion, which are closely related.²⁰ Harris (1973, 59) expands on this: 'The double burden of the memories of lost love and of the lost adolescent dream provoke an extreme reaction: the wish to erase memories completely in a state of oblivion, the *olvido* of the collection's title'. Thus, we find in this book the first modulation of Cernuda's poetics of memory, linked to the frustration of the amorous ideals of his youth and ending in a tragic desire to forget everything. In fact, the loss and evocation of the 'eternal present' of childhood is, according to Philip Silver (1965, 29), 'the keystone of Luis Cernuda's poetics'. This can be clearly seen in the prose poems collected in the 1942 volume *Ocnos*, in which the theme of memory (especially in relation to childhood) plays a fundamental role. One of the best examples is the poem 'Las campanas' ('The bells'):

Quisiera saber qué razón tiene el atractivo del recuerdo. La misma palabra recuerdo, ¿designa toda la emoción intemporal de un evocar que sustituye lo presente en el tiempo con un presente suyo sin tiempo? Porque ahí está

lo misterioso: que nazca una emoción al adumbrarse en la memoria el recuerdo de algo que ninguna emoción parecía suscitar cuando actualmente ocurriera, como la luz que recibimos de una estrella no es la luz contemporánea de ese momento, sino la que de ella partió en otro ya distante.²¹ (Cernuda 1993, 606)

Here, it is already clear that Cernuda's thought is strongly influenced by his study of English Romantic poetry: his formulation is very close to the famous Wordsworthian definition of poetry as remembered experience.²² On the other hand, there is also a shift from the poetic model of Juan Ramón Jiménez to a conception much closer to the model of Antonio Machado, in whose work, as we have seen, the memory of the poet's Sevillian childhood is also central. But in Machado's case, the memory of childhood is replaced and supplemented by the memory of youthful love in the 'Leonor cycle', something that Cernuda was unable to experience in its entirety. There is no memory of a full and satisfying love, so the frustration of love tends to be identified with the loss of childhood ideals. The fundamental difference between the two poets, however, is that while Machado died without knowing the post-war period and exile, Cernuda continued to develop his poetic work for more than two decades, introducing some relevant changes.

Las nubes (*The Clouds*, 1940) was begun in Spain and completed during Cernuda's exile in England. It is often regarded as his first mature book of poetry and, in any case, represents a significant milestone in the development of his poetic style. It is also the first collection to contain poems with a historical theme linked to Spain's past. His attachment to his homeland and the painful memory of exile is something that recurs in what Neira and Pérez Bazo (2002, 133) have called 'the cycle of war', a group of poems in which we can see the development of Cernuda's poetics of memory during those crucial years. The composition entitled 'Tris-teza del recuerdo' ('Sadness of memory') provides some of the keys to this evolution, notably in its fifth stanza: '¿Quién dice que se olvida? No hay olvido. / Mira a través de esta pared de hielo / Ir esa sombra hacia la lejanía / Sin el nimbo radiante del deseo'.²³ (Cernuda 1993, 287). In *Donde habite el olvido* we have seen that oblivion was conceived as an extreme solution, parallel to death, to the problem of the dissatisfaction of desire, to the conflict between reality and desire that gives its name to Cernuda's entire poetic project. Now, however, the impossibility of forgetting is explicitly declared, as the memory of the old love revisits the poet in his dreams. But it is no longer the living body he had celebrated in the verse of his youth, but only a shadow, stripped of desire, which disappears without a trace when he wakes up alone in his bed. The 'ghosts of desire' that gave the title to a poem in *Donde habite el olvido* seem to have become literal apparitions in his mature poetry.²⁴

This new vision of love, equally hopeless and bitter, but now historicised and open to memory, is conditioned by Cernuda's experience of exile.²⁵ In this way, the memory of love merges with the memory of his homeland, as can be seen in poems such as 'Un español habla de su tierra' ('A Spaniard speaks of his land'), where the poet evokes 'Los castillos, ermitas, / Cortijos y conventos, / La vida con la historia, / Tan dulces al recuerdo'²⁶ (Cernuda 1993, 310). The result is an idea of Spain that no longer corresponds to the real Spain, but only to a remembered Spain, always mediated by memory and mythicised by the unfulfilled longing for love: this idealised vision of his lost country is what Cernuda calls Sansueña.²⁷

The type of poetry he would develop in later books such as *Como quien espera el alba* (*Like Someone Waiting for the Dawn*, 1947) or *Vivir sin estar viviendo* (*Living Without Being Alive*, 1949) has been well explained by Coleman (1969, 116): Cernuda always starts with a certain life experience, working it out through memory, and proceeds to objectify it in some dramatic character. The result is an impersonal, 'epic' form of poetry that constructs successive masks and figures in order to allegorise the poetic self, to distance itself from the experience and to be able to analyse it in a profoundly meditative tone. This also explains Cernuda's growing interest in the metaphysical poets, whose representative in the Spanish tradition he considered Francisco de Aldana (1537–1578).

Cernuda's discomfort with his country and his cultural heritage is a long-standing theme in his later work, and extend to his last collection of poems, *Desolación de la Quimera* (*Desolation of the Chimera*, 1962). However, in his last collection of prose poems, *Variaciones sobre tema mexicano* (*Variations on a Mexican Theme*, 1952), there is a significant change that leads the poet to a personal reconciliation with his own tradition. Once again, this reconciliation takes place through the power of memory: upon settling in Mexico, the poet recognises all the elements he longed for in his native Andalusia, which in a way takes him back to his lost childhood.²⁸ In a composition such as 'Lo nuestro' ('What is Ours'), Cernuda describes the dusty and dilapidated villages he sees as soon as he crosses the Mexican border—villages whose children

immediately evoke ‘painful’ memories of Sansueña: ‘Recuerdos de tu tierra, también pobre y también grave’²⁹ (Cernuda 1993, 629). The poem ends, however, with a celebration of the spiritual richness that underlies this material poverty, where the poet recognises ‘his people’, his compatriots. It is for this reason that Cernuda succeeds in avoiding the condescension characteristic of the European colonial gaze, for he acknowledges Mexico as a fundamental component in the understanding of Spain and criticises those Spaniards who disregard the Hispanic legacy in the Americas. This is an aspect otherwise entirely absent from the works of Machado and Gil de Biedma. Thus, the Mexican theme of Cernuda’s book, which can in many ways be seen as the culmination of his poetics of memory, is none other than the reunion of the old exile with his lost homeland. For Cernuda, Sansueña now lives on in the remains that Spain left behind in America.

Jaime Gil de Biedma: I remember life, but where is it

The poetic work of Jaime Gil de Biedma (1929–1990) belongs to the so-called generation of the 1950s and, more specifically, to the Barcelona School (that includes Carlos Barral and José Agustín Goytisolo, among others).³⁰ Gil de Biedma published only three volumes of poetry, which were later collected under the title *Las personas del verbo* (‘The Persons of the Verb’). The brevity and compactness of his work has led many critics to believe that it underwent no poetic evolution (Beltrán Almería 1994, 306), although this opinion must be nuanced. One of the elements that strengthens this unity is precisely the theme of memory, which adopts and develops approaches that we have already seen in Machado and Cernuda, two of the poets who most influenced Gil de Biedma and his group.

Once again, in Gil de Biedma’s first published book, we find the theme of memory linked to the nostalgic recovery of childhood.³¹ In this case, however, childhood is not only a ‘lost paradise’, but is also negatively connoted by the memory of war. In fact, the poet belongs to a generation labelled ‘the children of war’, because their childhood coincided with the Spanish Civil War. In Gil de Biedma’s case, there is a certain ‘guilty conscience’ because he was born to a wealthy family that did not directly feel the harmful effects of the war, so the evocation of his childhood is often presented with an ironic distance. In his poem ‘Infancia y confesiones’ (‘Childhood and Confessions’), we find this sense of guilt expressed through a parodic revision of Machado’s well-known verses quoted above: ‘Mi infancia eran recuerdos de una casa / con escuela y despensa y llave en el ropero ...’³² (Gil de Biedma 2010, 122).

But the poetics of memory in Gil de Biedma’s work is best represented in the narrative poems he would later write, often in the form of dramatic monologues. This format is taken from the English lyric tradition, from writers such as Wordsworth, Browning, Eliot and Auden, whose influence has been repeatedly emphasised by scholars.³³ In this respect, Gil de Biedma was the first in Spain to follow the way paved by Cernuda in the previous generation. Our poet, however, goes one step further, creating a split between the poetic self that speaks and the narrative self that is the subject of the poem, a device that characterises some of his best compositions. A poem from his second book, *Moralidades* (*Moralities*, 1966), which is one of his most famous compositions, constitutes a perfect example of this procedure. ‘*Barcelona ja no és bona, o mi paseo solitario en primavera*’ (‘Barcelona is no longer good, or my solitary walk in springtime’) describes the poet’s parents strolling through Barcelona in the years before the war. What is striking about this poem is the perspective adopted by the poet, who narrates the episode from the outside, but who is also present in the scene because he is still in his mother’s womb. The point of view of the poetic self in the present tends to merge with the impossible memory of the child in the womb: ‘Así yo estuve aquí / dentro del vientre de mi madre, / y es verdad que algo oscuro, que algo anterior me trae / por estos sitios destartados’³⁴ (Gil de Biedma 2010, 156).

This type of literary device points us to what Letamendía (2013, 47) calls ‘exercises of unreality’. In fact, Gil de Biedma uses the poetic recreation of experience, in the sense theorised by Robert Langbaum (1957), to problematise his own access to the past and, in this way, to question his own identity. The use of memory to recreate a fictional past thus becomes an ironic and even self-critical process, as Quance (1987, 294) suggests: ‘Indeed, Gil de Biedma cannot recall his past without subverting his own effort to derive the pleasure of self-recognition from it, without using irony to deflate nostalgia as an absolute poetic virtue’.

This literary approach is sharpened in Gil de Biedma’s last collection, with the evocative title *Poemas póstumos* (*Posthumous Poems*, 1968). In compositions such as ‘*Contra Jaime Gil de Biedma*’ (‘Against Jaime Gil

de Biedma') or 'Después de la muerte de Jaime Gil de Biedma' ('After the Death of Jaime Gil de Biedma'), the splitting of the poetic self reaches its limits.³⁵ The poet will give free rein to what Bagué Quílez (2016, 36) calls a fictionalised autobiography, to the point of 'killing' his own literary character. In this way, the poet will represent his own suicide through the literary creation of an impossible personal memory: that of the one who narrates his own death. This confirms what Mangini (1977, 99) says about the 'ghostly' character of the past in Gil de Biedma's poetry. This is a theme that comes from Machado's last period, from the poems and reflections collected under the name of his heteronyms. In this case, however, Gil de Biedma does not resort to an alternative identity, as is customary in dramatic monologue. It is his own identity that is fictionalised and thus compromised by the invention of an alternative memory. In this way, the invented alternative memory may even seek to replace the authentic memory that forms the poet's personal identity. This is why his last poems seem to be written 'posthumously', as if the figure of Jaime Gil de Biedma had already passed away, leaving only a depersonalised voice to reflect on the passage of time. The poem 'De senectute' ends with a line that sums up all his poetics: 'De la vida me acuerdo, pero dónde está' (Gil de Biedma 2010, 250): 'I remember life, but where is it'.

Conclusion

This examination of three of the most important Spanish poets of the twentieth century reveals a theme that is common to all three, but which is developed in a personal and characteristic way by each of them, according to their interests and their life circumstances. This theme is memory, which, as we have seen, occupies a central position in each of their works. In fact, this conclusion can be understood in relation to the aforementioned research by José Olivio Jiménez, whose main proposition is that time is the principal concern of a large part of contemporary Spanish poetry. From the representatives of the so-called generation of 1898, such as Machado or Unamuno, to the post-war poetic generations, and the avant-garde attempts of authors of the generation of 1927, such as Cernuda himself, and of course the exiled poets, the tearing apart of the irreversible passage of time, with the personal and social loss that it entails, has been a constant in contemporary Spanish literature.

This awareness of the passing of time, however, is always articulated through what we have called the poetics of memory: the literary representation of a past time and its recovery (including its dreaming or invention) from the poet's present. The theme of childhood as an unrecoverable golden age, the theme of the lost or deceased loved one, the theme of exile and nostalgia for the homeland, and the theme of the construction of personal and social identity: all are combined in different ways in the verses of Antonio Machado, Luis Cernuda, or Jaime Gil de Biedma, and offer a rich panorama of how memory can become poetic matter. At the same time, this poetry presents a complex reflection on the limits of subjectivity and the construction of personal identity: the poetic self becomes problematic, and the memory that sustains it is questioned in a metaliterary game. In this way, contemporary Spanish poetry, with its obsession with the passage of time and its subjective recovery, proves to be an ideal object of study for the emerging field of memory studies, which can contribute to the characterisation of this powerful poetic and aesthetic current that still awaits unified research.

Notes

1. A substantial body of literature has emerged around this notion, giving rise to the concept of autobiographical memory. See, at least, Robinson (1986), Nelson (2003), Ender (2005) and Brockmeier (2025). The majority of studies on this topic, however, privilege narrative as the literary form par excellence in the construction of autobiographical memory. In this article, I will seek to demonstrate that poetry can play an equally significant role.
2. However, according to Milevski and Wetenkamp (2022, 198), 'the potential of literary theory for a more systematic approach to Memory Studies has not yet been fully realized.' Milevski and Wetenkamp's paper provides a comprehensive overview, with an updated bibliography, of the relations between memory studies and literary studies.
3. On the *sphragis* in ancient poetry understood as an autobiographical graft and its importance in the particular case of Ovid, see Fredericks (1976).
4. See the reassessment of the theories of the autobiographical pact undertaken by Allamand (2018), where it is rightly emphasised that the well-known definition of autobiography as a 'retrospective prose narrative' was

- not intended by Lejeune as a proposal but merely as a representative sample of the definitions found in dictionaries and encyclopaedias.
5. 'Yes, I remember you, happy and clear afternoon, / almost spring, / afternoon without flowers, / when you brought me / the good smell of mint, / and of the good basil, / that my mother had in her pots.' (All translations are my own.)
 6. The most detailed commentary on this poem is by Moreno Castillo (2015, 240–265). Aznar Anglés (2002) offers a commentary on the text from the perspective of involuntary memory, which is connected to Machado's Bergsonism.
 7. 'Did it pass? Over its fields still wanders the ghost / of a people who put God before war.'
 8. Although Machado himself occasionally tried to minimise the influence of the French philosopher, his presence can be felt throughout his work, as Eugenio Frutos (1960) has shown. Moreover, Havard has argued that Machado may well have been familiar with Bergson's work before his trip to France since *Matter and Memory*, translated into Spanish in 1900, was 'Bergson's best known text in Spain in those vital years' (Havard 1983, 210). See also Glendinning (1962).
 9. 'My childhood is memories of a courtyard in Seville, / and a clear orchard where the lemon tree ripens; / my youth, twenty years in the lands of Castile; / my history, some events I don't want to remember.'
 10. This is the kind of phenomenon that Bousoño (1962, 172–176) calls 'temporal superimposition', presenting it as a feature of contemporary poetry and citing a poem by Machado as a paradigmatic example. It is the poetic phenomenon that occurs when one moment in time is projected onto another, which in Machado's case happens through memory.
 11. 'With the first lilies / and the first roses in the orchards, / on a blue afternoon, climb up to the Espino, / to the high hawthorn where her land is ...'
 12. 'Of all the memories, only / the illustrious gift of dream evocation is worthwhile.'
 13. For Machado, memory did not serve to recall past memories, but dreams, as Zubiría (1959, 97) has noted. Cerezo Galán (1975, 114) also points out that in Machado's poetry dreaming operates through procedures analogous to those of memory.
 14. Some critics have seen the change in Machado's work as a reaction to the 'dehumanised' conceptual poetry that emerged in Spain from the 1920s (Lázaro Carreter 1977, 125). In fact, the young poets of the time (the generation of 1927) followed the teachings of Juan Ramón Jiménez rather than those of Machado, as we shall see.
 15. This relevance has been noted by critics such as Michel Ugarte (1986, 333): 'Memory and its counterpart, oblivion, occupy a primordial place in Cernuda's poetry.' However, as we shall see, the theme undergoes significant changes throughout his work.
 16. On the theme of oblivion in Cernuda, in addition to the aforementioned chapter by Zubiaur with its useful classification, see also the more recent study by Larios Aznar (2023).
 17. 'Wandering beggar, remembering, desiring.'
 18. In 'Poemas para un cuerpo' ('Poems for a body'), the theme of love – which is explicitly presented as homosexual – is also consistently mediated by the theme of memory. See Cernuda (1993, 469–485).
 19. 'It is not love what dies, / it is us. / First innocence / Abolished in desire, / Forgetting itself in another forgetfulness, / Rhymes intertwined, / Why live if one day you disappear?'
 20. Jiménez (1972, 159) identifies two meanings in Cernuda's idea of oblivion: one refers to the concrete negation of a vital experience, while the other is an 'absolute negation' that corresponds to death. These are not two distinct senses, so any partial forgetting will be a miniature form of death. Talens (1975, 291) also considers that in Cernuda, oblivion is equivalent to death.
 21. 'You would like to know what the reason for the appeal of memory is. Does the word memory itself denote all the timeless emotion of an evocation that replaces the present in time with a timeless present of its own? For therein lies the mystery: that an emotion is born when in the memory darkens the recollection of something that did not seem to arouse any emotion when it actually happened, just as the light we receive from a star is not the contemporary light of that moment, but the light that came from it at another, already distant, moment.'
 22. The importance of the English poetic tradition in the development of Cernuda's work has been well studied (Bellver 1983; Hughes 1988; Insausti 2000; López García 2005). The main lesson he drew from the English poets was the objectification of the lyrical self, which he took from Eliot and conveyed through the dramatic monologue of Robert Browning, whose work he translated into Spanish. He also translated poems by Marvell, Blake, Wordsworth, Keats, and Yeats into Spanish.
 23. 'Who says there is forgetting? There is no forgetting. / Look through this wall of ice / Go that shadow into the distance / Without the radiant nimbus of desire.'
 24. For these reasons, I cannot agree with Bernard Sicot (2003, 53) when he states that *Las nubes* shows a happy, even euphoric memory. Sicot's own analysis of the poem 'Un español habla de su tierra' (2003, 67–69) contradicts this thesis.
 25. Indeed, Silver (1965, 189) has pointed out that Cernuda, as a member of the generation of 1927, lacked a 'his-torical sense'. However, his experience in exile from 1938 onwards made him aware of temporality and he incorporated it into his poetry, often by displaying himself as a historical figure in his dramatic monologues.
 26. 'The castles, hermitages, / Farmhouses and monasteries, / Life with history, / So sweet to remember.'

27. In the poem ‘Ser de Sansueña’ (‘Being from Sansueña’), Cernuda (1993, 417) refers to his homeland as the ‘madrastra / Original de tantos, como tú, dolidos / De ella y por ella dolientes’ (‘the stepmother / Original of so many, like you, who mourn / Of her and for her’). This brings us back to the same appellation that, as we have seen, Machado reserved for Castile when speaking of the decadence of Spain: stepmother of humble louts. On this topic, see Díaz Ventas (2020, 19–20).
28. In the words of Silver (1965, 81), ‘In Mexico as in the Andalusia of childhood the experience of the moment as eternal present is once more possible.’ Thus, if Sansueña was seen as a kind of lost paradise, Mexico will become an ‘Eden regained’. For the first time in his poetic career, in *Variaciones sobre tema mexicano* memory becomes something positive for Cernuda.
29. ‘Memories of your land, also poor and also grave.’
30. The symbolic beginning of this generation of poets is usually dated to 1959, when they went to Collioure to pay homage to Antonio Machado on the twentieth anniversary of his death. This is why they are also called the ‘Col-lioure generation’ (Riera 1988, 17).
31. This collection of poems, entitled *Compañeros de viaje* (*Fellow Travelers*, 1959), has often been associated with the social poetry of post-war Spain. However, the themes and general tone of Gil de Biedma’s early poems go far beyond the clichés of social poetry and are more akin to a poetics of time: ‘The theme of time passing dominates this book, fitting it into a general current of Spanish poetry of the late 1950s’ (Debicki 1982, 124).
32. ‘My childhood was memories of a house / with a school and a pantry and a key in the cupboard ...’
33. Maqueda Cuenca (2003, 48–49) has stressed Gil de Biedma’s debt to Eliot’s poetics, and in particular to the idea of the distance between the poet and his poem. The same idea that gives the title to his complete poetic work, *Las personas del verbo*, could be related to Eliot’s essay entitled ‘The Three Voices of Poetry’. Walsh (2004, 111), citing the same essay by Eliot, has underlined the importance of the English poet in constructing the literary ‘mask’ that hides Gil de Biedma’s identity in his most mature poetry.
34. ‘So I was here / in my mother’s womb / and it’s true that something dark, something previous / brings me to these shabby places.’
35. For a detailed analysis of this poetic splitting in *Poemas póstumos*, see Rovira (1986, 219–227).

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References

- Aguirre, José María. 1973. *Machado, poeta simbolista*. Madrid: Taurus.
- Allamand, Carole. 2018. “The Autobiographical Pact, Forty-Five Years Later.” *European Journal of Life Writing* 7:51–56. <https://doi.org/10.5463/ejlw.7.258>
- Aznar Anglés, Eduardo. 2002. “La memoria involuntaria y el sentido de la actividad artística. Comentario al poema VII de *Soledades* de Antonio Machado.” *Analecta Malacitana* 25 (2): 623–633.
- Bagué Quílez, Luis. 2016. “La importancia de llamarse Jaime: identidad privada y memoria colectiva en la poesía de Gil de Biedma.” *CELEHIS* 31:35–50. <https://fh.mdp.edu.ar/revistas/index.php/celehis/article/view/1750>.
- Bellver, Catherine G. 1983. “Luis Cernuda and T. S. Eliot: A Kinship of Message and Motifs.” *Revista de Estudios Hispánicos* 17 (1): 107–124.

- Beltrán Almería, Luis. 1994. "Tiempo y espacio en la lírica: el caso de Jaime Gil de Biedma." *Epos: Revista de filología* 10:299–322. <https://doi.org/10.5944/epos.10.1994.9889>
- Bousoño, Carlos. 1962. *Teoría de la expresión poética*. Madrid: Gredos.
- Brewster, Anne. 2005. "The Poetics of Memory." *Continuum* 19 (3): 397–402. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10304310500176875>.
- Brockmeier, Jens. 2025. *Beyond the Archive: Memory, Narrative, and the Autobiographical Process*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Cerezo Galán, Pedro. 1975. *Palabra en el tiempo: Poesía y filosofía en Antonio Machado*. Madrid: Gredos. Cernuda, Luis. 1993. *Poesía completa. Volumen I*. Barcelona: Siruela.
- Coleman, Alexander. 1969. *Other Voices: A Study of the Late Poetry of Luis Cernuda*. Chapel Hill: University of North Carolina Press.
- De Ros, Xon. 2015. *The Poetry of Antonio Machado: Changing the Landscape*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Debicki, Andrew P. 1982. *Poetry of Discovery: The Spanish Generation of 1956–1971*. Lexington: The University Press of Kentucky.
- Díaz Ventas, Álvaro. 2020. "El tema de España en la poesía del exilio de Luis Cernuda. De la madre a la madrastra." *Philobiblon: Revista de Literaturas Hispánicas* 11 (11):9–30. <https://doi.org/10.15366/philobiblion2020.11.001>.
- Ender, Evelyne. 2005. *Architexts of Memory: Literature, Science, and Autobiography*. Ann Arbor: University of Michigan Press.
- Erll, Astrid. 2008. "Cultural Memory Studies: An Introduction." In *Cultural Memory Studies: An International and Interdisciplinary Handbook*, edited by Ansgar Nünning, Astrid Erll, and Sara Young, 1–18. Berlin: De Gruyter.
- Erll, Astrid. 2011. *Memory in Culture*. London: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Fredericks, Betty R. 1976. "Tristia 4.10: Poet's Autobiography and Poetic Autobiography." *Transactions of the American Philological Association* 106:139–54. <https://doi.org/10.2307/284096>.
- Frutos, Eugenio. 1960. "El primer Bergson en Antonio Machado." *Revista de Filosofía* 19 (73–74): 117–168.
- Gaxha, Blerina Rogova. 2022. "Literature as Testimony: The Poetics of Memory in Poetry." *Primerjalna književnost* 45 (3): 145–159. <https://doi.org/10.3986/pkn.v45.i3.09>.
- Gil de Biedma, Jaime. 2010. *Obras. Poesía y prosa*. Barcelona: Galaxia Gutenberg.
- Gill, Jo, and Melanie Waters. 2009. "Poetry and Autobiography." *Life Writing* 6 (1): 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14484520802550262>.
- Glendinning, Nigel. 1962. "The Philosophy of Henri Bergson in Machado's Poetry." *Revue de Littérature Comparée* 36:50–70.
- Görbert, Johannes, Marie L. Hansen, and Jeffrey Ch. Wolf. 2021. "The Self in Verse. Exploring Autobiographical Poetry. Editorial." *The European Journal of Life Writing* 10:1–12. <https://doi.org/10.21827/ejlw.10.37636>.
- Gullón, Ricardo. 1986. *Una poética para Antonio Machado*. Madrid: Espasa-Calpe.
- Hamburger, Käte. 1993. *The Logic of Literature*. Bloomington: Indiana University Press.
- Harris, Derek. 1973. *Luis Cernuda: A Study of the Poetry*. London: Tamesis.
- Havard, Robert G. 1983. "Antonio Machado's Knowledge of Bergson before 1911." *Neophilologus* 67 (2): 204–214. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02334228>.
- Hughes, Brian. 1988. *Luis Cernuda and the Modern English Poets: A Study of the Influence of Browning, Yeats, and Eliot on His Poetry*. Alicante: Universidad de Alicante.
- Hutman, Norma Louise. 1969. *Machado: A Dialogue with Time. Nature as an Expression of Temporality in the Poetry of Antonio Machado*. Albuquerque: University of New Mexico Press.
- Insausti, Gabriel. 2000. *La presencia del romanticismo inglés en el pensamiento poético de Luis Cernuda*. Pamplona: EUNSA.
- Jiménez, José Olivio. 1972. *Cinco poetas del tiempo: Vicente Aleixandre, Luis Cernuda, José Hierro, Carlos Bousoño, Francisco Brines*. Madrid: Ínsula.
- Ladrón, Morales, and María Soledad. 2004. "La temporalidad bergsoniana en las estéticas de Antonio Machado y James Joyce." *Bells: Barcelona English Language and Literature Studies* 13:1–12. <http://hdl.handle.net/10017/33760>.
- Langbaum, Robert. 1957. *The Poetry of Experience: The Dramatic Monologue in Modern Literary Tradition*. New York: Random House.
- Larios Aznar, Jordi. 2023. *La tarea de las palabras: Ortega y Schopenhauer en la obra de Benjamín Jarnés, Pedro Salinas y Luis Cernuda*. Palma de Mallorca: Leonard Muntaner.
- Lázaro Carreter, Fernando. 1977. "El último Machado." In *Curso en homenaje a Antonio Machado*, 119–134. Salamanca: Universidad de Salamanca.
- Lejeune, Philippe. 1975. *Le pacte autobiographique*. Paris: Seuil.
- Lerro, Menotti. 2017. *Autobiographical Poetry in England and Spain, 1950–1980*. Cambridge: Scholars Publishing.
- Letamendía, Nora. 2013. "La reconstrucción del pasado en la poesía de Jaime Gil de Biedma." *CELEHIS* 25:33–50. <https://fh.mdp.edu.ar/revistas/index.php/celehis/article/view/820>.
- López García, Dámaso. 2005. "Luis Cernuda y las letras inglesas: el caso Eliot." In *Perfil de Cernuda*, edited by Javier Huerta Calvo, Emilio Miró González, and Emilio Peral Vega, 55–80. Madrid: Verbum.
- Machado, Antonio. 1979. *Poesías completas*. Madrid: Espasa-Calpe. Mangini, Shirley. 1977. *Jaime Gil de Biedma*. Madrid: Júcar.

- Maqueda Cuenca, Eugenio. 2003. *La obra de J. Gil de Biedma a la luz de T. S. Eliot y el pensamiento literario anglosajón*. Jaén: Universidad de Jaén.
- Milevski, Urania, and Lena Wetenkamp. 2022. "Introduction: Relations between Literary Theory and Memory Studies." *Journal of Literary Theory* 16 (2): 197–212. <https://doi.org/10.1515/jlt-2022-2022>.
- Mironescu, Andreea. 2022. "Generations, Contemporaneity, and Intersectionality in Literary History." *Studia Universitatis Babeş-Bolyai* 67 (3): 107–120. <https://doi.org/10.24193/subbphil.2022.3.16>.
- Moreno Castillo, Enrique. 2015. *Sobre dieciocho poemas de Antonio Machado*. Sevilla: Renacimiento.
- Neira, Julio, and Javier Pérez Bazo. 2002. *Luis Cernuda en el exilio. Lecturas de "Las nubes" y "Desolación de la Quimera"*. Toulouse: Presses Universitaires du Mirail.
- Nelson, Katherine. 2003. "Self and Social Functions: Individual Autobiographical Memory and Collective Narrative." *Memory* 11 (2): 125–136. <https://doi.org/10.1080/741938203>.
- Olney, James. 2014. "Some Versions of Memory/Some Versions of *Bios*: The Ontology of Autobiography." In *Autobiography. Essays Theoretical and Critical*, edited by James Olney, 236–267. Princeton: Princeton University Press.
- Quance, Roberta. 1987. "Writing Posthumously: Jaime Gil de Biedma." *Anales de la literatura española contemporánea* 12 (3): 291–309. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/27741822>.
- Rapport, Frances, and Graham Hartill. 2010. "Poetics of Memory: In Defence of Literary Experimentation with Holocaust Survivor Testimony." *Anthropology and Humanism* 35 (1): 20–37. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1548-1409.2010.01050.x>.
- Ribbans, Geoffrey. 1997. "Machado's *Ciclo de Leonor*." In *Negotiating Past and Present: Studies in Spanish Literature for Javier Herrero*, edited by David Thatcher Gies, 76–91. Charlottesville: Rookwood Press.
- Riera, Carme. 1988. *La Escuela de Barcelona*. Barcelona: Anagrama.
- Robinson, John A. 1986. "Autobiographical Memory: A Historical Prologue." In *Autobiographical Memory*, edited by David C. Rubin, 19–24. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Rovira, Pere. 1986. *La poesía de Jaime Gil de Biedma*. Barcelona: Edicions del Mall.
- Sánchez Barbudo, Antonio. 1954. "El pensamiento de Abel Martín y de Juan de Mairena y su relación con la poesía de Antonio Machado (Conclusión)." *Hispanic Review* 22 (2): 109–165. <https://doi.org/10.2307/470966>.
- Sicot, Bernard. 2003. *Exilio, memoria e historia en la poesía de Luis Cernuda*. Ciudad de México: Fondo de Cultura Económica.
- Silver, Philip. 1965. *"Et in Arcadia ego": A Study of the Poetry of Luis Cernuda*. London: Tamesis.
- Takolander, Maria. 2017. "Confessional Poetry and the Materialisation of an Autobiographical Self." *Life Writing* 14 (3): 371–383. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14484528.2017.1337502>.
- Talens, Jenaro. 1975. *El espacio y las máscaras: introducción a la lectura de Cernuda*. Barcelona: Anagrama.
- Ugarte, Michael. 1986. "Luis Cernuda and the Poetics of Exile." *Modern Language Notes* 101 (2): 325–341. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2905766>.
- Urrutia, Jorge. 1976. "Bases comprensivas para un análisis del poema *Retrato*." *Cuadernos Hispanoamericanos* 304–307 (2): 920–943.
- Walsh, Andrew S. 2004. *Jaime Gil de Biedma y la tradición angloamericana*. Granada: Universidad de Granada.
- Watt, Mary A. 2021. *Dante's Golden Legend: Auto-hagiography in the Divine Comedy*. Macon: Mercer University Press.
- Zubiaur, Ibon. 2002. *La construcción de la experiencia en la poesía de Luis Cernuda*. Kassel: Reichenberger.
- Zubiria, Ramón de. 1959. *La poesía de Antonio Machado*. Madrid: Gredos.